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Purpose and scope of the deliverable

The objective of deliverable D4.8 is to report on all the dissemination activities implemented since the commencement of the project from 01 January 2020 until 31 March 2021. This second Dissemination Report describes the dissemination activities of the project as a whole, as well reports on the activities carried out by each partner.

This report continues and complements the first Dissemination Report issued in August 2020 (D4.7) and is available on the project's website in its open area

(<http://www.spotprojecth2020.eu/reportsandoutcomes>).

Document history

Version	Date	Description
<i>0.1</i>	<i>01 Apr 2021</i>	<i>Draft of the SPOT Dissemination Report II</i>
<i>0.2</i>	<i>09 Apr 2021</i>	<i>Comments of partners</i>
<i>0.3</i>	<i>16 Apr 2021</i>	<i>The second version of the first annual summary dissemination report</i>
<i>1.0 (final)</i>	<i>29 Apr 2021</i>	<i>Approved by PMB and the Coordinator</i>

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1. Centralized dissemination efforts

The three key activities targeting the public are (1) the online presence ensured through a website and social media sites, (2) the annually published newsletter and (3) the podcasts. The Coordinator and WP4 leader manage the overall dissemination/exploitation of the project results and coordinate the dissemination activities. Partners are responsible for the execution of the local actions.

1.1. Project Website

The SPOT homepage (www.spotprojecth2020.eu) is the main online presence of the SPOT project. It has been created by WP4 and MENDELU in M2 with a public and a restricted area. The public area of the website is the main dissemination channel, it is used to inform about the project activities, events and publications. The partners continuously contribute scientific content to ensure its periodic update and extension and provide translations for a multi-lingual information channel.

The initial design of SPOT-web was done by KRTK using the service of the freely available WIX platform (www.wix.com); the domain name has been purchased and is administered by MENDELU. The public part of the site is placed at <http://www.spotprojecth2020.eu/>. The SPOT homepage is optimized both for desktop computers and mobile Android and Apple devices.

Figure 1. Illustration of the SPOT homepage

The statistics of the website (Figure 2. and 3.) show a growing interest and the success of individual partners in the local dissemination activities. As seen in Figure 2. until March 22, 2021, the homepage had more than 1000 distinct visits. The daily visits on average are between 10 and 20.91% of the visits stem from new visitors, most of them are directly accessing the homepage. The top referring site is Google.

The percentage of new visitors is relatively high, which shows that raising awareness about the project was successful so far. This statistic demonstrates as well that the homepage is an adequate reference point for partners and the public audience for providing and getting information. To show the activities of the project WP4 periodically updates the homepage with the news. As reported by March 22, 2021, the team

published altogether 72 news on the website. The analysis of updates to the homepage shows that these updates, especially the e-Newsletter published in December, led to a spike in the number of visitors. Considering that the homepage has been running for a year the number of distinct visits is below the desirable. As the project advances, we expect an increase in the number of uploads and consequently in the number of visitors. A detailed strategy and a collective effort from all partners is needed to increase the number of uploads and visits. The statistics indicate that social media sites are not fully exploited as referring sites and a stronger emphasis needs to be put on sharing the contents of the homepage on Facebook and Twitter.

To evaluate the improvements we advise the PMB to formulate KPIs and attribute expected/desirable values to these for the website and social media activities. To reach the desired number of visitors we advise setting a strategy in which every partner has to contribute to the content with short blogs, news etc. to the website in a set period.

One of the ways to increase the visibility of the SPOT website and its media is the new activity arranged by the coordinator together with IMPACTOUR and SmartCultTour H2020 projects leaders where an agreement was set to deeper our cooperation also within dissemination actions. The meeting between all three projects dissemination leaders is currently organized.

Figure 2. Statistics of the SPOT homepage

Figure 3. Statistics of the SPOT homepage

1.2. Social Media

The objective of social media presence and press releases is to reach as many people as possible. The project is present on the social media platforms Twitter (<https://twitter.com/H2020Spo>) and Facebook (<https://www.facebook.com/SPOTprojectH2020/>). WP4 members established these profiles and use them to disseminate project news. The statistics of social media sites are shown in Figures 4. and 5. The number of total followers on Facebook is 94, all of them are organic followers of the site. Based on the performance of SPOT Facebook the increase in the number of followers is slight. We observed a higher number of followers after updates regarding relevant milestones of the project e.g. the e-Newsletter and the Executive Summary. The posts with the highest reach are related to SPOT events and the e-Newsletter. When creating the Facebook page for the project WP4 intended to signpost audiences to the SPOT homepage, which based on Figure 2. had low success.

We conclude that short, informative posts with pictures had the highest reach, therefore we need to increase the number of short and more frequent posts on Facebook. Based on the data we suggest the PMB formulate a strategy to increase the SPOT Facebook visibility e.g. through a short campaign. Language barriers also need to be addressed. To reach more people we recommend partners to summarize the Facebook posts in their language on the Facebook sites of their Institute and signpost their audiences to the SPOT Facebook and the SPOT homepage. To increase engagement we encourage partners to comment, share and like the posts on Facebook. To become visible to relevant audiences the SPOT Facebook and every partner need to follow, like or tag groups or individuals that could be relevant or related to the project.

Figure 4. Statistics of the Facebook site of SPOT

On Twitter short comments, announcements and news are posted. Over 91 days the SPOT Twitter (Figure 4.) earned 1300 impressions. Impressions mean the total number of times SPOT content was displayed to people, regardless, whether it was clicked on or not. On average the posts reached 14 people per day. Twitter has 20 inputs but only 16 followers, which shows that the contents uploaded to this platform are not reaching the relevant users. The statistics in Figure 4. show that engagement grew for a few days after uploading content. The goal for the rest of the project is to increase the number of followers and impressions with regular uploads. We encourage partners to create short, informative posts and to promote the Twitter of the project.

Figure 5. The statistics of SPOT Twitter

1.3. The e-Newsletter

The purpose of the annual electronic newsletter is to disseminate the results of the SPOT project among different stakeholders and the general public. Based on the list of addresses collected by the MENDELU team and other partners, the newsletter is distributed to policymakers and other stakeholders across Europe throughout the project duration.

WP4 introduced the first annual E-Newsletter (Available at: <http://www.spotprojecth2020.eu/media-and-downloads?pgid=kiOfInm8-5b05d438-755d-40d8-8163-4d4a08598060>) in December 2020. The first electronic newsletter was created to inform interested parties, including stakeholders, about the achievements of the project. The general objective in the design of the newsletter was to have a recognizable layout with varied articles intended to report the progress of partners. In its visual layout, it incorporates the same visual elements, that Work Package 4 used during the set up of the website and social media sites. Thereby it is recognizable as a SPOT product.

The first newsletter contained eight sections, as can be seen below:

- Section 1: SPOT at a glance
- Section 2: Project news
- Section 3: Fieldwork during COVID-19 pandemic – As seen by our partners
- Section 4: Case study area news
- Section 5: Conferences and events
- Section 6: Publications
- Section 7: SPOT in the media
- Section 8: Tourism in Europe

The eight sections were arranged around four main themes: sections 1 and 2 provided general information about the project. Sections 3 and 4 were the more informative parts of the newsletter, reporting on the activities of partners and the news related to the case study areas. Sections 5, 6 and 7 were centred around the dissemination activities of the project, for example, conference appearances. Section 8 provided an outlook on tourism in Europe.

The newsletter starts with the section ‚SPOT at glance‘, which contains the general description of the project, supported by a map with all partners of the Consortium. The section ‚Project news‘ is intended to report on the overall progress of the project, with news from the main Work Packages.

The section ‚Fieldwork during COVID-19 pandemic‘ reports on the fieldwork period of the tourist, residential and entrepreneur surveys. It focuses on how partners faced the challenges brought on by the COVID-19 pandemic. ‚Case study area news‘ contains short articles about events and measures that contribute to cultural tourism in the case study areas and news about specific responses to the COVID-19 pandemic.

The sections ‚Conferences and events‘; ‚Publications‘ and ‚SPOT in the media‘ relate to the dissemination of project results through publications in peer-reviewed journals and presentations at conferences.

‚Tourism in Europe‘ provides an overview of the results of studies done on the effects the COVID-19 pandemic has on tourism. It also provides information on the results of the „sister projects“ of SPOT and how they can add to the discussion about possible solutions to revitalize tourism.

The newsletter has been advertised through the SPOT social media pages, the team also published it on the homepage and sent it to the subscribers of the SPOT website. Additionally, the annual newsletter is distributed to a list of 483 people curated by MENDELU.

Figure 6. Illustration of the e-Newsletter

1.4. The Podcasts

KRTK and MENDELU interviewed and recorded researchers for podcasts and published these on the project website. Four researchers have been interviewed and 2 podcasts have been published.

The podcast recorded by KRTK is about a complex research program in Hungary focusing on the effect of COVID-19 on the tourist consumer behaviour of the Hungarian population. The most important results of the research were discussed in the depth. Professor Milada Štátná representing MENDELU participated in an audio live streaming interview about the SPOT research project.

Professor Milada Štátná participated in an audio live streaming interview about the SPOT research project on Czech Radio Plus, in a 60-day session.

Prof. Milada Štátná presented the SPOT project H2020 within the live streaming program 'Events in Regions' (Brno), prepared by the Czech Television.

Czech national TV ČT1 recorded the information about SPOT project, including field work of two Czech team members during the cultural event in Velké Bílovice (the South Moravian region) on

Podcasts

Complex research in Hungary: The effect of COVID-19 on the tourist consumer behaviour of the Hungarian population

The research consists of 2 parts, on the one hand a literature review and on the other hand an online questionnaire. The survey ran from late April to early June 2020 and a total number of respondents were 736. Tourism comprises around 10% of the Hungarian GDP, therefore it is important to examine the current changes. The experts agreed that, the coronavirus pandemic is not only a crisis, but also a chance.

Figure 7. Illustration of the podcasts

1.5. Impact

These key activities help to raise public awareness, facilitate close cooperation between the consortium partners and support the promotion of the Innovation Tool as a means for policymaking in disadvantaged as well as tourism overpressured regions.

2. Dissemination activities of partners

2.1. Publications

The individual SPOT partners already started to disseminate their scientific project results through publications in peer-reviewed journals and presentations at conferences as it is visible on the EU portal, but also on ZENODO, where a SPOT project Community was established and can be reached also on the SPOT website under the relevant section.

Scientific articles ensure the dissemination of links between already existing and newly generated knowledge across the scientific community and stimulate further research on benefiting from cultural tourism in disadvantaged regions and tourism overcrowded places. During the first year of the project, partners published 12 articles, and there were three mass-media publications.

Scientific articles:

- Nemčíková, M., Krogmann, A., Oremusová, D., Ambrosio, V., Mróz, F. (2020): Sv. Cyril a Metod a ich reflexia v krajine Slovenska, *Konštantínove listy/Constantine's Letters*, 13(1), pp. 224-236.
Source: UKF
- Petrikovičová, L., Krogmann, A., Fialová, D., Svorad, A. (2019): Intensive tourist-related urbanisation impacts on a mountain village: The case study of Veľká Lomnica in Slovakia, *Geographia Polonica*, 92(4), pp. 395-408.
Source: UKF
- Krogmann, A., Mróz, F., Dvořáková Líšková, Z., Dubcová, A., Nemčíková, M., Oremusová, D. (2020): Possibilities for Developing Beer Routes in Slovakia, *Studies of the Industrial Geography Commission of the Polish Geographical Society*, 34(3), pp. 36-52.
Source: UKF

Peer-reviewed articles:

- Vaishar, A., Šťastná, M. (2020): Impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on rural tourism in Czechia Preliminary considerations, *Current Issues in Tourism*, DOI: 10.1080/13683500.2020.1839027
Source: MENDELU
- Vaishar, A., Šťastná, M., Zapletalová, J., Nováková, E. (2020): Is the European countryside depopulating? Case study Moravia, *Journal of Rural Studies*, 8, pp. 567-577.
Source: MENDELU
- Vaishar, A., Šťastná, M., Ryglová, K., Rašovská, I., Zámečník, S. (2020): CULTURAL TOURISM AS A POSSIBLE DRIVER OF RURAL DEVELOPMENT IN CZECHIA. WINE TOURISM IN MORAVIA AS A CASE STUDY, *European Countryside*, 12(3), pp. 292-311.
Source: MENDELU
- Šťastná, M.; Vaishar, A.; Brychta, J.; Tuzová, K.; Zloch, J.; Stodolová, V. (2020): Cultural Tourism as a Driver of Rural Development. Case Study: Southern Moravia, *Sustainability*, 12(21), 9064
Source: MENDELU
- Mitrică, B., Șerban, P.R., Mocanu, I., Damian, N., Grigorescu, I., Dumitrașcu, M., Dumitrică, C. (2021): Developing an Indicator-Based Framework to Measure Sustainable Tourism in Romania. A Territorial Approach, *Sustainability*, 13(5), 2649
Source: IGAR
- Harfst, J., Sandriester, J., Fischer, W. (2021): Industrial Heritage Tourism as a Driver of Sustainable Development? A Case Study of Steirische Eisenstrasse (Austria). *Sustainability*, 13(7), 3857

Mass-media publication/mass communication:

KRTK, MENDELU (2020): The e-Newsletter I. <http://www.spotprojecth2020.eu/media-and-downloads?pgid=ki0flnm8-5b05d438-755d-40d8-8163-4d4a08598060>

- MENDELU (2021): Executive Summary: February 2021. <https://zenodo.org/record/4564237#.YFSbxmhKhPY>
- IOER (2021): Mehr Kulturtourismus in der Lausitz? https://www.lieberose-oberspreewald.de/Media/public/Homepage/Mitteilungsblatt/2021_03.pdf

Conference papers:

- Mitrică, B., Mocanu, I., Grigorescu, I., Dumitrașcu, M. (2020): Cultural tourism in Romania – a general outline of the conceptual framework. Proceedings of the GEOLINKS Conference Vision for new horizons. International Conference on Environmental Science, Book 2, Vol. 2, Section GREEN DESIGN AND SUSTAINABLE ARCHITECTURE
Source: IGAR
- Hardi, T. (2020): Határon átnyúló ökoturisztikai lehetőségek a Duna „belső deltájá”-ban - Cross-border possibilities of ecotourism in the "inner Delt of Danube". Kreativitás, változás, reziliencia. III. Nemzetközi Turizmusmarketing Konferencia Tanulmánykötet (Proceedings of the III. International Tourism Marketing Conference: Creativity, change, resilience.
Source: KRTK
- Oremusová, D., Krogmann, A., Nemčíková, M., Némethová, J. (2020): Utilization of the potential of Orava Castle in development. Proceedings of the Aktuální problémy cestovního ruchu: Overtourism - riziko pro destinace Conference.
Source: UKF
- Rech, G., Migliorati, L. (2020): Nuove sfide al turismo culturale in un paesaggio letterario. Il caso di Langhe, Monferrato e Roero e il Covid-19 nel progetto SPOT. Proceedings of the Regions Between Challenges and Unexpected Opportunities (XLI AISRe Conference)
Source: UNIVR

2.2. Scientific conferences and workshops

Partners published the project results at eight scientific conferences and eight workshops. This task was limited by COVID-19 measures, however, it is expected to have it done online during the next two years too if the situation not change. By doing so, the consortium will be able to disseminate the results more widely and better exploit their full potential.

Scientific conferences:

- EUROMED 2020 (2020.11.02-04.)
Participating partners:
MENDELU: Possible directions of rural tourism development in the light of Covid-19: Case study: South Moravia
UNIABDN: Online Cultural Activity and Fan Tourism in Scotland
- EURORURAL '20 - SMART COUNTRYSIDE FOR THE 21st CENTURY (2020.09.01-04.)
Participating partner:
MENDELU: Impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on rural tourism in Czechia Preliminary considerations

- 2nd Tourist Forum: Tourism in the border-lands of the Karkonosze, Iżera Mountains and Lusatia (2020.09.30)
Participating partner:
UWR
- 28th International Geographical Conference Geographical aspects of the Central European area Creativity of regions (2020.10.04)
Participating partner:
UKF
- 5th International Conference Physical Activity in the Mountain Areas of Poland and World (2020.11.09-10.)
Participating partner:
UWR: The importance of cultural resources for the development of tourism on the example of selected communes in Western Sudetes
- Regions Between Challenges and Unexpected Opportunities (XLI AISRe Conference) (2020.09.02-04.)
Participating partner:
UNIVR: Nuove sfide al turismo culturale in un paesaggio letterario. Il caso di Langhe, Monferrato e Roero e il Covid-19 nel progetto SPOT
- AESOP YA (2021.03.31.)
Participating partner:
UL: Key speaker - Naja Marot
- GEOLINKS Conference Vision for new horizons. International Conference on Environmental Sciences (2020.10.05-07.)
Participating partner:
IGAR: Cultural tourism in Romania – a general outline of the conceptual framework

Workshops:

- SPOT - SMARTCULTUR – IMPACTOUR (2020.11.27.)
Participating partners:
MENDELU: Cultural Tourism and its future in 5-year time
WR, UL, UNIVR, IGAR, UWR, UB
- SPOT Cultural Tourism Scientific Workshop of the Consortium (2020.09.07.)
Participating partners:
all partners of the Consortium
- SPOT Kick-off meeting (2020.01.28-29.)
Participating partners:
all partners of the Consortium
- DIGIT Workshop (2020.03.27.)
Participating partner:
UNIABDN: Media Tourism in Scotland

- Joint Consortium meeting about Cultural Tourism (2020.06.08.)
Participating partners:
UNIABDN, UAegean
- 11th Ethnographic Film Festival of Athens - Cultural Landscape and Cultural Heritage Workshop (2020.11.09.)
Participating partner:
UAegean: The Cultural Landscape
- Breakfast at Sustainability's (2021.11.07.)
Participating partners:
UL, IGAR
- MESTUR Workshop (2021.02.19.)
Participating partner:
UL

2.3. Networking activities of partners

Collaboration with European, national/regional actors will allow the partners to integrate existing knowledge, present project findings and discuss these with key stakeholders within their region. Six workshops are planned for the entire project duration. The first workshop was the kick-off meeting serving as a starting point of the project. The last workshop will be the closing meeting summarizing the project. The first workshop was held in Brno. Workshops 2-5 will be organized by the respective WP leaders (all of them were online during 2020) and workshops 1 and 6 by MENDELU. The content of individual workshops contains public presentations of problems (with presentations of stakeholders, where possible), including online round tables and technical excursions to selected case study regions. These excursions will be organised by the local partners (after the COVID-19 limitations are over). Main actors/stakeholders from the selected region, but also other ones, if possible, will be invited to participate.

The consortium members closely co-operate with the stakeholders and regional partners. BIU held meetings with officeholders at the national, regional and local levels. WUR arranged regional collaborations: meetings with different stakeholders for 1) introducing the SPOT project, 2) getting permission for live fill-in sessions with tourists in "Kinderdijk and 3) for introducing our surveys on websites of stakeholders and in newsletters of stakeholders in the Dutch language for online survey. To increase the visibility of the project, they communicated with the staff of the municipalities of Molenlanden and Alblasserdam and with the program manager of Kinderdijk2030. There was also contact with Interest association Liveability Kinderdijk. UNIVR similarly introduced the project to stakeholders in Alba and later on presented the first results of the project to them. UNIABDN also held a presentation and a lecture for the University of Ljubljana. UAegean, UL and UB also had networking activities meant to raise awareness about the project. KRTK held meetings with the teams' most important stakeholders: with the cultural director of the Fort System of Komárom and with the director of Pons Danubii EGTC.

2.4. Project leaflet

The project leaflet is an important dissemination material during the introduction of the project to potential stakeholders and networking with interested parties. KRTK together with MENDELU prepared and issued a special leaflet about the project (available at <http://www.spotprojecth2020.eu/media-and-downloads>). Translated into 15 languages it has been distributed to the stakeholders to inform them about the SPOT project. The leaflet contains a short presentation of the project, the study areas, the main tool prepared by

the project, addresses and other useful information. Partners can download these proofs from FTP server and print out these leaflets as needed. The leaflets are available on the project website (and also on the project Facebook and Twitter pages).

Figure 8. Illustration of the SPOT leaflet

2.5. Impact

The dissemination activities carried out by partners are described in Table 1., divided by the type of activity. Despite the situation caused by the Covid-19 pandemic partners engaged in several dissemination activities. The number of participants to a conference was 10, to workshops 20. All partners contributed to the social media updates with short news, publications and photos.

Table 1. Dissemination activities of partners

Type of dissemination activity	Number
Organisation of Conference	1
Organisation of a Workshop	3
Press release	18
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication	16
Exhibition	0
Flyer	9
Training	4
Social Media	46
Website	11
Communication Campaign (e.g. radio, tv)	10
Participation in a Conference	10
Participation in a Workshop	20
Participation in an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	7
Participation in activities organised jointly with other EU projects	8
Other	16

As a result of partners' dissemination activities, the estimated number of persons reached in the context of all dissemination and communication activities is around 123 thousand persons. The detailed assessment of the target groups (Figure 9.) shows that partners managed to involve 146 policy-makers, 3350 members of the civil society, more than a thousand researchers from the scientific community, more than 75 thousand individuals through press releases and their research and almost 41 thousand people through media.

Figure 9. Structure of SPOT-project audiences reached in 2020

3. Prospects for 2021-2022

3.1. Web-based Resource Center

By the end of 2021, a Web-based Resource Centre will be established (D4.6) by KRTK and MENDELU teams. MENDELU together with MTA KRTK will develop this tool as a part of the project website www.SPOTprojectH2020.eu. It will be communicated via all other dissemination activities targeted at policymakers and other stakeholders.

The Resource Centre will provide:

- information for scientists, policy-makers, stakeholders, NGOs, practitioners etc.
- data and maps related to the impact of cultural tourism in the case study areas
- presentation of research results
- policy recommendations / strategies
- examples of good practice
- the interpretative model for stakeholders' use

The consortium will seek further funding to maintain the Web tool after the project ends (MENDELU will guarantee its maintenance for min. 5 years after the project ends). The key to the success of the Resource Centre is to formulate policies and development strategies based on the research findings and provide them actively to the relevant political institutions.

3.2. Scientific events and conferences

One or two Science Events are planned which will stimulate the integration and utilisation of the research findings in the relevant public and include the following features: exhibition, screening of films, presentations, panel discussions. It will be aimed at a wider public – integration in (joint) university curricula, student or lecturer exchange, joint publications or conference attendances (sessions, lectures etc.). Due to the COVID-19 limitation, the majority of foreseen events are cancelled or moved online thus our project members are aware to adjust to that properly.

While some of the information should be national/regional specific, some of the information forms could be used at all events in each research area (e.g. podcast, see above). In regions, where general “Science Weeks” or “Science Nights” etc. are organised, those events could be used as further dissemination opportunities of the project (probably online).

The closest coming event where the SPOT project coordinator will participate is **IMPACTOUR ReDiscover Europe Workshop on 9 May 2021** under the auspices of the Portuguese Government and with full collaboration from the Slovenian Government. The ReDiscover Europe Workshop will provide a unique opportunity to discuss the role of sustainable Cultural Tourism in today’s Europe. Besides important keynote presentations the workshop will hold three key panel debates (with catalyst viewpoints from policy makers, scientific researchers, industry and cultural tourism practitioners): – Theme 1: Post-COVID cultural tourism – what have we learned, what might we do differently, an opportunity for Big / SMART Data? – Theme 2: People – accessibility, inclusion/exclusion, market needs – Theme 3: Technology – digital gateways, mobile interactive content / co-curation, dynamic modelling and tourism management.

Another online workshop is being organized by Dr. Rodrigo Martín Galán, Research Programme Officer from Research Executive Agency Established by the European Commission Unit C.1 - Inclusive, Innovative and Reflective Societies. **WORKSHOP ON THE STATE OF THE ART OF THE RESEARCH AND FUTURE PRIORITIES IN THE FIELD OF CULTURAL TOURISM** will take place on **16 June 2021**. The main points will be a Discussion on challenges and current problems in the research in this field and a Discussion on gaps in our knowledge and needs of the research in the field.

Conferences would include:

- EURORURAL '22, organized by Mendel University in Brno,
- AESOP annual conferences (2021, 2022),
- Regional Studies Association Annual Conference (2021, 2022),
- Warsaw Regional Forum (2021),
- 6th International Scientific Conference,
- ToSEE - Tourism in Southern and Eastern Europe (2021),
- European Sociological Association,
- International Sociological Association,
- International Society for Quality of Life Studies,
- International Association of Landscape Ecology (IALE),
- European Congress 2021,
- Net-work of Spatial Research and Planning in Central, Eastern, and South-Eastern Europe (2021),
- American Association of Geographers (AAG),
- Permanent European Conference for the Study of the Rural Landscape (PECSRL),

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- International Geographical Union (IGU) bi-annual meetings, regional and commissions' conferences,
 - EUGEO, EUROGEO,
 - Regional Studies Association events,
 - Association of European Border Regions conferences
 - UNESCO conferences,
 - The International Committee for the Conservation of the Industrial Heritage,
 - International Council on Monuments and Sites (ICO-MOS).

Individual partners will hold guest lectures (single lecture, term course or “bloc” course of 2 to 3 days) in the target countries to disseminate the research results within the scientific community, especially to the student body and to ensure scientific exchange.

3.3. Further activities

Two forthcoming newsletters will be published in 2021 and 2022 (D4.3 and D4.4). In every half year, a dissemination report will be written (D4.7–D4.10). We want to encourage the partner teams to prepare different kinds of dissemination material. During the project period, every team should provide a podcast, news etc. Having the first scientific results, we will publish more infographics, short news on our website and social media, as well as in the electronic newsletter. After the pandemic, we should strengthen the personal contacts among the project partners, as well as between the partners, stakeholders and other professionals.